

Molecular modeling and potentiometric study of some metal complexes of *o*-vanilineglutamate Schiff base

M. Sivasankaran Nair*, C. Ravi Samuel Raj, D. Arish and S. Sudha Kumari

Department of Chemistry, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627 012, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : msnairchem@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 26 June 2009, revised 6 November 2009, accepted 17 November 2009

Abstract : The complexing behaviour of *o*-vanilineglutamate Schiff base ligand with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were investigated by semiempirical (AM1), molecular mechanics (MM+) and potentiometric methods. The results demonstrate that the Schiff base ligand is tertridentate in the MAB complexes. Both the molecular modeling and potentiometric studies indicate that the ligand is tridentate in the M(AB)₂ complexes.

Keywords : Semiempirical, molecular mechanics, potentiometry, Schiff base, computation.

Introduction

One of the most prominent and fascinating features of the metal complexes is its large variability of molecular geometry. Their geometrical flexibility depends not only on the metal ions, but also on the nature of the ligand¹. Many models were proposed to interpret and predict the structure of metal complexes. Among them molecular mechanics calculations are unique in many ways such as its higher applicability towards coordination chemistry and simplicity². Schiff base complexes of metal ions play important role in many biological reactions^{3,4}. The coordination chemistry of Schiff bases formed by amino acids is of considerable interest due to their biological importance⁵. There are ample studies on the metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from substituted salicylaldehydes and various amino acids⁶. However, little attention was made to their computational and solution state studies⁷⁻¹⁶. The present study describes the molecular modeling and equilibrium chemistry on the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with *o*-vanilineglutamate (*o*-van-glu) Schiff base derived from *o*-vanillin (*o*-van) and glutamic acid (glu).

Results and discussion

Computational studies :

o-van-glu Schiff base ligand : The numbering pattern and structure of the ligand is given in Fig. 1. The ground state geometry of this ligand is optimized by semiempirical AM1 Hamiltonian. Its important Mulliken atomic elec-

tron density is given in Table 1. It shows that the ligand is potentially tetradentate and capable of binding through N₈, O₁₂, O₁₇ and O₁₈ atoms. Further the binding ability of the ligand is confirmed by calculating its protonation energy using MM+ method. The total energy for the mono protonated ligand is listed in Table 2. The mono protonation energy shows that the binding ability of the donor atoms in the ligand is of the order : O₁₂ > O₁₇ > O₁ > N₈. This order of binding ability is agreeable with the Mulliken atomic charge density. The results (Table 4) show that the imino nitrogen-phenolic oxygen, imino nitrogen- α -carboxylato oxygen and imino nitrogen- γ -carboxylato oxygen are distorted from planarity respectively by 18°, 48° and 42°.

MAB type of complexes : The important geometrical parameters of MAB complexes are given in Table 4 and the structure is given in Fig. 1. In this complex, the ligand can coordinate in a tetradentate manner involving imino nitrogen (N₈), phenolic oxygen (O₁₅), α -carboxylato oxygen (O₁₂) and γ -carboxylato oxygen (O₁₇) atoms. In the complex, the imino nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms are more planar as compared to the ligand. There is less deviation in the dihedral angles between imino nitrogen- α and γ -carboxylato oxygen atoms as compared to that in the ligand. The total energy given in Table 3 shows that the metal complexes follow Irving-Williams order of stability : Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}.

Note

$O_{12}-O_{18} > N_8-O_{17}-O_{18} > O_{12}-O_{17}-O_{18}$. Thus, it can be concluded that the most probable donor groups in *o*-van-glu for the tridentate binding are imino nitrogen (N_8), phenolic oxygen (O_{18}) and α -carboxylato oxygen (O_{12}). The stability of the metal complexes follows Irving-Williams order (Table 3).

Solution studies : Schiff base complexes of stoichiometry MAB, MAB_2 and $M(AB)_2$ in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and

Zn^{II} -*o*-van(A)-glu(B) systems and MAB in the Cu^{II} -*o*-van(A)-glu(B) have been detected.

Stability and structure of MAB complexes : The preferential formation of MAB over that of binary species can be illustrated by considering stepwise formation constants of various species. This is clearly evident in Scheme 1 showing the stepwise formation constants of

Table 3. Binding energy of *o*-van-glu complexes

<i>o</i> -Van-glu	Total energy (kcal/mol)			
	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
Tetradentate	78.0719	45.6197	36.4422	82.5944
Tridentate				
$N_8-O_{12}-O_{18}$	40.3459	39.6455	37.8207	44.1846
$N_8-O_{17}-O_{18}$	48.4290	48.0584	47.6433	49.5674
$O_{12}-O_{17}-O_{18}$	56.9509	56.9898	51.6086	64.5253
$N_8-O_{17}-O_{12}$	15.8280	15.5244	14.3910	19.7834

Scheme 1

Table 4. Important geometrical parameters of *o*-van-glu and its metal complexes

Ligand	Co^{II}	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Zn^{II}
MAB complex				
M- N_8	1.8242	1.8136	1.8323	1.9129
M- O_{17}	1.7794	1.7694	1.7893	1.8695
M- O_{18}	1.7685	1.7585	1.7778	1.8565
M- O_{12}	1.7939	1.7843	1.8045	1.8813
M- N_8-O_{18}	103.564	103.797	103.285	101.2690
M- $O_{17}-O_{18}$	109.537	109.119	109.222	110.4500
M- N_8-O_{17}	111.585	112.069	112.117	111.9950
M- N_8-O_{12}	110.719	110.706	110.777	110.602
$C_1-C_2-C_7-N_8$	-18.3032	-2.3835	-2.2663	0.6757
$C_7-N_8-C_9-C_{10}$	132.773	-67.8923	-62.4005	-67.8086
$C_7-N_8-O_9-C_{13}$	-42.1583	138.546	141.667	148.352
M(AB) ₂ complex				
M- $N_{8(1)}$	2.3862	2.3767	-	2.4749
M- $N_{8(2)}$	1.8503	1.8415	-	1.9306
M- $O_{17(1)}$	1.800	1.7911	-	1.8826
M- $O_{17(2)}$	1.7905	1.7817	-	1.8756
M- $O_{18(1)}$	1.8037	1.7949	-	1.8911
M- $O_{18(2)}$	1.7898	1.7948	-	1.8785
N_8-M-O_{18}	75.7853	76.0829	-	73.8949
$N_{8(2)}-M-O_{17(2)}$	98.2355	98.5401	-	93.3639
$N_{8(2)}-M-O_{17(2)}$	86.3268	86.111	-	78.6532
$N_{8(1)}-M-O_{18(2)}$	75.8477	76.2793	-	78.3987
$O_{17(1)}-M-N_{8(1)}$	90.1606	90.1118	-	92.1903
$O_{18(1)}-M-O_{17(2)}$	-7.5807	-7.6328	-	0.1639
$C_1-O_{18}-M-O_{17(2)}$				

the different species present in the $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$ system. If the MAB species is considered as a mixed ligand complex, then the statistically calculated overall formation constant¹⁷ for the CoAB species would be 7.57. But the experimental value is 10.5. This higher value can be explained by considering the strong inter-ligand interaction between the aldehyde group of $o\text{-van(A)}$ and the amino group of glu(B) to form a stable Schiff base ligand (AB), which coordinates the metal ion. Again, the $\log \beta_{\text{CoAB}}$ value of 10.25 (Table 5) is higher than that of 9.30

cently. Thus, CoAB_2 is a mixed ligand species involving the Schiff base (AB) and the amino acid (B) and it can be formulated as Co(AB)B , where the Schiff base (AB) is tetradentate. The $\log K_{\text{MAB}_2}^{\text{MAB}}$ values in Table 5 also suggest that the MAB_2 species can be represented as M(AB)B .

The M(AB)_2 complexes in the $\text{M}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$ systems are stable with high $\log \beta$ values (Table 4), which can be represented as a bis(Schiff base) complexes of the type M(AB)_2 . Here both the Schiff base ligands can coordinate terdently because the tetradentate binding of both

Table 5. Stability constants of $\text{M}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$ Schiff base complex systems

System	$\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MAB}_2}$	$\log \beta_{\text{M(AB)}_2}$	$\log K_{\text{MAB}_2}^{\text{MAB}}$	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MAB}}$
$\text{Co}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$	10.25	11.85	15.63	1.60	1.61
$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$	11.45	13.98	17.89	2.53	1.84
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$	16.20	-	-	-	2.21
$\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$	9.61	11.60	15.38	1.99	1.59

in the $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van-val}$ system⁶ by 0.95 units. This demonstrates that in the $o\text{-van-glu}$ system, all the four possible donor atoms of the Schiff base ligand (AB), viz. imino nitrogen, phenolic oxygen and two carboxylato oxygen atoms participate in complexation with metal ion. This would result in the formation of a highly stable Co(AB) complex which will have one five, one six and one seven membered chelate rings.

By putting forward the same arguments, it can be concluded from the stability constant data in Table 5 that in the MAB complexes in the Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van-glu}$ systems also the Schiff base ligand would function as tetradentate. The stabilization factor¹⁸, $\Delta \log K$ calculated for the M(AB) species in Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van-glu}$ systems (Table 5) follows the Irving-Williams order of stability.

Stability and structure of MAB_2 and M(AB)_2 complexes : The $\log \beta$ values (Table 5) computed for the MAB_2 complexes in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$ systems are much higher than that calculated¹⁹ for simple mixed ligand complexes without inter-ligand interaction. The $\log K$ value for the formation of CoAB_2 from CoAB is 1.60, whereas that for $\text{CoB} + \text{B} \rightleftharpoons \text{CoB}_2$ is 3.34. Hence, it can be expected that in the CoAB_2 species, the second glu(B) unit can coordinate the metal ion indepen-

dently. Schiff base ligands will lead to an effective coordination number of eight to M^{II} , which is improbable for $3d$ metal ions, in general. There are two possible structures for this species. The α -carboxylato group can coordinate along with the phenolic and imino nitrogen of the Schiff base ligand resulting in the formation of two five and two six membered chelate rings, whereas the coordination of γ -carboxylato group will lead to the formation of two five and two seven membered chelate rings. Among these, the former arrangement could be the preferred one because of steric factors in the latter. The computational studies also agree with this conclusion.

Species distribution :

The species distribution diagram in the $\text{M}^{\text{II}}-o\text{-van(A)-glu(B)}$ systems indicate that the formation of M(AB) is favored over that of binary species. In both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 systems, the M(AB) species are predominantly present in the pH range between 5–6.5 reaching a maximum of ~60% of the total metal ion. The M(AB)B species was found to be favored above pH 6.0 and reaches a maximum of ~30% of the total metal ion in the 1 : 1 systems, and ~35% in the 1 : 2 systems. In 1 : 1 systems, the formation of M(AB)_2 species was found to have a concentration maximum at pH 6.0, while in the 1 : 2 system M(AB)_2 is the predominant species between pH 6.0 to

6.5. Moreover in the 1 : 1 systems the maximum concentration of $M(AB)_2$ species is only $\sim 35\%$ whereas in the 1 : 2 systems the concentration reaches up to $\sim 70\%$ of the total metal ion. In order to demonstrate these trends, the species distribution diagram of Co^{II} -*o*-van-glu system is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Species distribution diagram for the Co^{II} -*o*-van-glu system.

Experimental

The semiempirical calculations were carried out using MOPAC 6 programme by AM1 Hamiltonian²⁰. The geometry was optimized by Eigen Vector Following Algorithm with the RMS gradient of 0.01 kcal/(Å mol). The molecular mechanics calculations were done using MM+ force field¹ in the Hyperchem 7 software. The geometry was optimized by Polake-Ribiere Algorithm with the RMS gradient of 0.01 kcal/(Å mol). The pH measurements were carried out at 25 °C and 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KNO₃ ionic strength under nitrogen with a Systronics pH meter (model 361, accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit). All the solutions were prepared with double-distilled water in grade A glassware. In the Schiff base complex equilibria, equilibrium has been found to attain very slowly and hence batch

wise titration was performed²¹. The pH data were analyzed using a computer program²² designed for the evaluation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The auxiliary data for the binary complexes required for the computation of the stability constants of the Schiff base complex systems under the present experimental condition were taken from literature²³.

Conclusion :

The present study comprises of both computational and solution chemistry of metal complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with *o*-van-glu Schiff base. The Cu^{II} forms only MAB complex, while other metal ions form MAB, MAB₂ and $M(AB)_2$ complexes. In MAB complexes the ligand is tetradentate. The MAB₂ species can be represented as $M(AB)B$. Both the ligand are tridentate in $M(AB)_2$ complexes.

References

1. P. Comba, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993, 123, 1.
2. S. K. Sahoo, S. E. Muthu, M. Baral and B. K. Kanungo, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2006, 63(A), 574.
3. D. E. Metzler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 485.
4. D. E. Metzler and E. E. Snell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 979.
5. K. D. Karlin, *Science*, 1993, 261, 701.
6. M. Amirasrl, K. J. Schenkb, A. Gorjic and R. Vafazadehed, *Polyhedron*, 2001, 20, 695.
7. M. S. Nair, S. S. Kumari and R. S. Joseyphus, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, 84, 739.
8. M. S. Nair, S. S. Kumari and M. A. Neelakantan, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, 12, 60.
9. R. S. Joseyphus and M. S. Nair, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, 62, 319.
10. M. S. Nair and R. S. Joseyphus, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2008, 70(A), 749.
11. M. Palanichamy and M. Anbu, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 1997, 109, 105.
12. H. Demirelli and F. Koseoglu, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2005, 34, 561.
13. C. Marina, G. Gordana, M. C. Dubravka, N. Predrag, H. Tomica, L. Ivan and N. T. Kajfez, *Polyhedron*, 2009, 28, 562.
14. J. C. Pessoa, S. Marcão, I. Correia, G. Gonçalves, A. Dörnyei, T. Kiss, T. Jakusch, I. Tomaz, M. Margarida, C. A. Castro, C. F. G. C. Geraldes and F. Avecilla, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, 3595.

15. T. Takayama, T. Sekine and H. Kudo, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 2003, **255**, 97.
16. W.J.O.-T. *THEOCHEM*, 2005, **715**, 79.
17. H. Sigel, *Angw. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 394.
18. D. L. Leussing and K. S. Bai, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 571.
19. H. Sigel, "IUPAC Coordination Chemistry-20", ed. D. Banerjea, Pergamon Press, Oxford, New York, 1980, 28.
20. J. J. P. Stewart, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1991, **12**, 320; J. J. P. Stewart, MOPAC, "A Semiempirical Molecular Modeling Program in : QCPE", 1983, **6**, 1990.
21. M. S. Nair, S. T. David and M. Anbu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 823.
22. D. Leussing and D. Hoppgood, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **32**, 505.
23. A. E. Martell and R. M. Smith, "Critical Stability Constants", Plenum Press, New York, 1974-1989, Vol. 1-6.